

Hybrid Provision of Energy based on Reliability and Resiliency by Integration of Dc Equipment

Work Package WP4

Grid planning and operation strategies

Deliverable D4.8

Simulation report on development of ACDC Hybrid Microgrids in parallel with existing distribution grid

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Table of Contents

Executive Summary	7
1. Introduction	8
1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document	8
1.2 Structure of the Document	8
2. Simulation Tool	9
2.1 Tool Introduction	9
2.2 LVDC configuration and voltage levels	9
2.3 Synthetic grid model	10
2.4 Line types	10
2.5 ACDC hybrid LV grid scenarios	11
2.6 Simulation Parameters	12
2.7 Results	13
3. Simulation Model	18
3.1 AC Grid Model.....	18
3.2 ACDC Microgrid Model.....	18
3.3 Power Flow Profiles	18
3.4 Complete Simulation Model.....	22
3.5 Scenarios	23
3.6 Results	24
4. Conclusions	30
References	31

List of Figures

Figure 1: a) LVDC unipolar line configuration (with metallic return conductor to prevent corrosion) and b) LVDC bipolar configuration for 4-conductor LV line.	10
Figure 2: Maximum transmission power vs line length cable type XAY2Y 4x150.	12
Figure 3: ACDC hybrid scenario 1a.	12
Figure 4: ACDC hybrid scenario 1b.	13
Figure 5: ACDC hybrid scenario 2.	13
Figure 6: Maximum Loading of LV feeder yearly simulation	15
Figure 7: LV urban 3 daily max. loading profile, Sept 16.	15
Figure 8: LV urban 3 daily min/max voltage, Sept 16.	16
Figure 9: LV rural 1 daily min/max voltage profile, Jun 23.	16
Figure 10: Maximum LV feeder input apparent power	17
Figure 11: Terni MV Feeder Power Factory Model.	19
Figure 12: Terni Pilot ACDC microgrid concept.	20
Figure 13: Terni Pilot AC critical loads profile (in MW) connected to hybrid ACDC microgrid.	20
Figure 14: Total Active Power of the components in the ACDC microgrid.	21
Figure 15: Terni Pilot EV load profile (in MW) connected to hybrid ACDC microgrid.	21
Figure 16: Power Factory model of AC grid with ACDC microgrid connected.	22
Figure 17: Voltage levels of the LV and MV terminals over a year.	24
Figure 18: Loading of the MV-LV transformer 5 over a year.	25
Figure 19: Voltage levels of the LV and MV terminals over a year with ACDC microgrid connected. ..	25
Figure 20: Loading of the MV-LV transformer 5 over a year with ACDC microgrid connected.	26
Figure 21: Comparison of the LV and MV terminals with different configuration of the AFEs.	26
Figure 22: Comparison of the MV-LV transformer 5 loading with different configuration of the AFEs. .	27
Figure 23: Direct comparsion of the loading of the MV-LV transformer 5 over a day.	27
Figure 24: Variation of all components within the ACDC microgrid.	29

List of Tables

Table 1: Recommended LVDC voltage levels. 10
Table 2: Detailed LV feeders in synthetic grid model. 11
Table 3: Simulation Parameter. 14

List of Abbreviations

AC	Alternating Current
ACDC	Alternating Current and Direct Current
AFE	Active Front End
AIT	Austrian Institute of Technology
API	Application Programming Interface
BESS	Battery Energy Storage System
DC	Direct Current
DEG	Distributed Energy Generation
DoA	Description of Action
DoD	Depth of Discharge
EV	Electric Vehicle
HV	High Voltage
LV	Low Voltage
LVAC	Low Voltage Alternating Current
LVDC	Low Voltage Direct Current
LVDG	Low Voltage Distribution Grid
MV	Medium Voltage
PV	Photovoltaic
QDS	Quasi Dynamic Simulation
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
VSC	Voltage Source Converter
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The incorporation of a greater number of Renewable Energy Sources (RES), the transition towards Distributed Energy Generation (DEG), and the evolving energy consumption patterns resulting from the electrification of transportation are set to reshape both electricity production and demand. The impact of these changes is particularly notable in the Low Voltage Distribution Grid (LVDG), where the increasing prevalence of Electric Vehicle (EV), the integration of small to medium-sized distributed RES like Photovoltaic (PV) systems, and the utilization of energy storage solutions such as Battery Energy Storage System (BESS) are transforming the landscape.

Today, a significant proportion of devices connected to the LVDG operate on Direct Current (DC). This includes powering common everyday devices like computers, cellphones, and EVs. DC offers the advantage of energy storage capability and is unaffected by reactive power and is not requiring synchronization. These characteristics simplify the control of DC systems. RES such as PV systems and fuel cells inherently produce DC power, making their integration into a DC network more efficient. The partial operation of the distribution grid using DC instead of Alternating Current (AC) has emerged as a viable strategy for cost-effective management in the context of future grid scenarios aligned with international decarbonization objectives.

Utilizing a simulation tool for techno-economic analysis with synthetic test grid models, it has been demonstrated that the conversion of Low Voltage Alternating Current (LVAC) grid feeders to a DC configuration represents a viable solution for alleviating overloading and reducing voltage fluctuations. These issues are primarily induced by factors such as the integration of EVs, PV, and heightened energy demand. The simulation tool showcases the flexibility of rapidly hybridizing complex grid models within DigSILENT Power Factory. It highlights the potential advantages of integrating DC technology into Low Voltage (LV) grids, particularly when near-capacity limits are reached.

A simulation model was developed based on the DC pilot installation in Terni, encompassing the nearest Medium Voltage (MV) feeder from the public grid. It integrates various grid planning tools and conducts Quasi Dynamic Simulation (QDS). The Terni pilot site was simulated using Power Factory because the existing simulation tool lacked the capability to model the Alternating Current and Direct Current (ACDC) microgrid with two connection points via transformers. The analysis has brought to light that the AFE plays a decisive role in AC grid support by the DC grid, as shown by the current AC grid and the proposed DC configuration. In the context of this demonstration site, it is essential for the converters to possess the capability to supply reactive power to effectively support the AC grid.

As part of our efforts, we conducted an extensive investigation with the primary objective of identifying the most suitable configuration for the ACDC microgrid. Our ultimate goal was to maximize self-consumption while minimizing reliance on the AC grid. The resulting optimal configuration not only allowed for the integration of more AC loads but also reduced the required battery power output.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

According to the Description of Action (DoA) (HYPERRIDE Description of Action, 2020), this report focuses on development of ACDC Hybrid Microgrids in parallel with existing distribution grids. A simulation tool was utilized, which has been specifically designed to facilitate techno-economic assessments of hybrid ACDC LV networks that encompass both AC and DC components, with a particular emphasis on grid planning considerations. The distinguishing feature of this simulation tool is its ability to methodically transform LVAC infrastructure into DC equivalents and then conduct simulations of the hybridized grid using Power Factory, by leveraging its integrated Python Application Programming Interface (API). It has already been presented in (Caujolle et al., 2019) that through self-designed models in the EPSL Modelica library, the hybridization of the grid can lead to reduced losses in most scenarios. In contrast to this approach, the simulation tool we are currently utilizing is based on Power Factory, a well-established and widely-used power system analysis software.

To support a modular approach to grid planning for applied hybrid ACDC microgrids, alongside existing MV-LV AC grids, the DC pilot installation located in Terni (Work Package (WP) 8) was modeled, including the closest MV feeder from the public grid. In addition to the development and simulation of specific hybrid ACDC grid scenarios using Power Factory, other grid planning tools such as the Component Sizing Tool (D3.4) were integrated into the analysis. In this context, QDS were performed. It is worth noting that the scope of the investigation did not encompass the dynamic behavior of the system nor its control mechanisms.

1.2 Structure of the Document

This document is organised as follows: Section 1 provides information about the report content whereas Section 2 introduces the simulation tool. In Section 2.5, we present the predefined scenarios incorporated into the simulation tool. Subsequently, in Section 2.6, an enumeration of the selected simulation parameters is presented. In Section 2.7, a summary of the simulation tool's outcomes is provided. Section 3 introduces the simulation model of the Terni pilot installation. In Section 3.5 the simulation scenarios are defined. Section 3.6 summarises the results of the performed simulations. Furthermore, the deliverable is concluded in Section 4.

2 Simulation Tool

2.1 Tool Introduction

The simulation tool was initially developed in the scope of a master's thesis (Fuchs, 2020) and the findings, along with a comprehensive evaluation, were presented (Fuchs, Jambrich, & Brunner, 2021) as part of the HYPERRIDE project. Here, we provide a concise summary of the most important details and results on the tool. This tool is engineered to facilitate techno-economic assessments of hybrid ACDC LV networks incorporating both AC and DC components, with a particular emphasis on grid planning considerations. This is accomplished through the implementation of quasi-dynamic simulations within the Power Factory environment. This simulation tool is characterized by its capacity to systematically convert LVAC infrastructure into LVDC equivalents and subsequently simulate the hybridized grid using Power Factory, all under the control of its integrated Python API. A web-based interface is provided to users, serving as an interface for configuring simulation parameters and initiating the simulation process. In order to facilitate meaningful comparisons, the tool is equipped to simulate both purely AC and hybrid ACDC systems under identical conditions. Furthermore, it supports the integration of EVs and PV into the grid, necessitating the execution of two additional simulations to account for the increased loads introduced by these components. Upon obtaining simulation results, users are offered the opportunity to conduct economic analyses via the same user interface, with the ability to customize key parameters. It is important to underscore that this description primarily emphasizes the technical dimensions of the tool, with the economic simulation aspect reserved for a more detailed exploration in subsequent discussions. For a deeper understanding, the following sections provide comprehensive elucidations of the implemented DC configurations, various simulation scenarios, and the overall grid configuration. Our primary focus remains firmly rooted in the intricate technical aspects of the tool, with the economic simulation aspect acknowledged for future investigation.

2.2 LVDC configuration and voltage levels

DC distribution lines and feeders within the simulation tool necessitate a specific configuration choice: they can be set up as either unipolar or bipolar systems. The starting point for this configuration is the LVAC lines, which are utilized for LVDC. This configuration decision relies on the utilization of 4-conductor LVAC lines, as delineated in Figure 1 within the simulation tool. In the unipolar configuration, it's important to note that the LV power cables are certified for a maximum operating voltage of $900 V_{DC}$ concerning their potential in reference to the earth. In the case of parallel AC lines, there is a notable deviation from the unipolar setup; instead, three conductors are employed for both the positive and negative conductors, characteristic of bipolar DC operation. At present, no established criteria exist for the operational voltage parameters of LVDC grids. The suggested operating voltage ranges for Low Voltage Direct Current (LVDC) distribution grids, which operate at voltages less than $1500 V_{DC}$ as per the technical report IEC TR 63282:2020, can be found in Table 1. All findings presented were generated through simulations conducted at the maximum nominal recommended voltage level of $\pm 700 V_{DC}$.

Figure 1: a) LVDC unipolar line configuration (with metallic return conductor to prevent corrosion) and b) LVDC bipolar configuration for 4-conductor LV line.

Table 1: Recommended LVDC voltage levels.

Configuration	U_{nom}	U_{min}	U_{max}
unipolar	350 V _{DC}	320 V	380 V
unipolar	700 V _{DC}	640 V	760 V
bipolar	±350/700 V _{DC}	640 V	760 V
bipolar	±700/1400 V _{DC}	1280 V	1500 V

2.3 Synthetic grid model

The synthetic grid model used encompasses all components spanning from the High Voltage (HV) transmission level (220 kV) to the distribution levels (110 kV and 20 kV, both in urban and rural), extending to the LV connection points. This comprehensive model includes detailed representations of ten LV feeders (as shown in Table 2), incorporating a total of 190 loads. These loads are modeled to accurately reflect the characteristics of typical rural and urban LV feeders within the European distribution grid (presented in (Khan, Henein, & Brunner, 2020), available at (Khan, 2019)). In addition to a radial LV grid configuration, the model also offers an option for a meshed LV topology. Furthermore, it includes equivalent loads that operate in AC at all network levels, representing the portions of the grid not directly under investigation. The load and PV profiles provided are based on European data (Khan, 2019), offering a 15-minute resolution for yearly load and PV profiles. The EV profiles are constructed to emulate realistic static charging patterns (Stahleder, Nöhner, Lehfuss, & Müller, 2018).

2.4 Line types

The simulation tool provides an automated means of assessing the maximum power transmission capacity concerning line length for both AC and DC operation across various line types, all while considering line losses. Within the utilized synthetic grid model, the rural LV grid predominantly comprises typical European overhead line configurations, while the urban grid is characterized by the usage of typical LV cables. In Figure 2, we observe a typical LV cable denoted as XAY2Y 4x150, where our investigation focuses on determining the maximum transmission power as a function of line length, up to 1400 V_{DC} in a bipolar configuration. By adhering to the recommended DC voltage levels specified in Table 1, our analysis has corroborated that

Table 2: Detailed LV feeders in synthetic grid model.

Feeder	Max Length [m]	Nr of lines	Nr of loads
LV rural 1	1056	26	16
LV rural 2	430	22	14
LV rural 3	549	30	17
LV rural 4	610	34	22
LV rural 5	220	2	1
LV urban 1	430	28	25
LV urban 2	370	22	19
LV urban 3	360	30	26
LV urban 4	400	34	31
LV urban 5	450	21	19

the transmission capacity for the specific line type XAY2Y 4x150 can be effectively doubled when operated at 1400 V_{DC} in a bipolar configuration (± 700 V_{DC}), compared to its operation at 400 V_{AC}. When factoring in voltage fluctuations, denoted as dV, within the range of $\pm 25\%$, it becomes evident that the active power for extended LV feeders exceeding 2000 meters is significantly enhanced by factors of ten when utilizing DC-based systems operating at ± 700 V_{DC}.

2.5 ACDC hybrid LV grid scenarios

The simulation tool integrates predefined scenarios, for the purpose of converting LV transmission lines and feeders from an AC configuration to a DC configuration. This transformation results in the establishment of hybrid LV distribution networks. For the ACDC hybrid grid simulations, the following scenarios are considered:

Scenario 1: DC Lines and AC loads

This scenario closely resembles the current situation, wherein pre-existing power transmission lines undergo a conversion to DC. From the customers perspective, there is no noticeable difference, as all modifications occur on the grid infrastructure. The visual representation of this scenario is illustrated in Figure 3.

In the context of the test grid simulation, an additional scenario was incorporated, wherein the electrical loads remain connected to the AC grid, while EV and PV are directly linked to the DC grid, as depicted in Figure 4.

Scenario 2: DC Lines and Loads

In this scenario, electrical loads are directly connected to the DC system. This configuration is favored due to its higher efficiency and cost-effectiveness. Figure 5 illustrates this scenario. For the presented results, Scenario 2 was chosen, as it demonstrates the most promising attributes for LVDC grid applications.

Figure 2: Maximum transmission power vs line length cable type XAY2Y 4x150.

Figure 3: ACDC hybrid scenario 1a.

2.6 Simulation Parameters

Table 3 presents the simulation parameters that have been made available. The values listed in the "Simu Params" column are subsequently applied in the simulation results presented later.

Figure 4: ACDC hybrid scenario 1b.

Figure 5: ACDC hybrid scenario 2.

Efficiency improvements have been quantified for various components such as loads, PV systems, and EV chargers when they are directly connected to a DC power source. Numerous studies have demonstrated that, depending on a range of factors, efficiency gains in the range of 1% to 20% can be achieved for different household loads when connected directly to DC. For the scenario being presented, an average value of 10% was adopted. It is worth noting that the efficiency gain for EV chargers and PV converters is estimated to be considerably smaller, approximately 1%. This is since both applications involve ongoing optimization efforts to enhance efficiency, with further developments expected in this direction. The maximum apparent power input at the feeder, denoted as S_{in_max} occurs only briefly during specific time intervals within all DC feeders. Therefore, the rated power of the Voltage Source Converter (VSC) is set at $0.9 \cdot S_{in_max}$ taking into consideration the dynamic overload capacity of ACDC converters. The levels of EV and PV penetration, as well as load scaling, have been selected to represent potential future scenarios in which the existing grid approaches its capacity limitations.

2.7 Results

In the subsequent section, we present the simulation outcomes obtained through the incorporation of the previously explained variables within the synthetic grid model. Figure 6 illustrates a comprehensive decrease in the maximum loadings across all simulated feeders when transitioning from 400 V_{AC} to 1400 V_{DC}. The introduction of supplementary PV infeed and EV loads notably impacts the loading of the LV rural 1 feeder, while the inclusion of prospective loads has the potential to further reduce maximum loading in other feeders.

When assessing the maximum loading over the course of a simulated year, it becomes evident that feeder LV rural 1 and LV urban 3 are susceptible to overloading violations, as illustrated in Figure 6. Figures 7 and 8 present comprehensive data regarding maximum loading, as well as minimum and maximum voltage profiles, for a specific day, September 16th, coinciding with the peak loading period for LV urban 3. While the instances of overloading represent transient

Table 3: Simulation Parameter.

Parameter	unit	Simu Params	Range	Description
Grid model	-	w/	w/ or w/o	Synthetic grid model w/ or w/o equiv. loads
LV feeder	-	1 – 5 rur. 1 – 5 urb.	1 – 5 rur. 1 – 5 urb.	LV feeder selection (rural and urban) for conversion to DC
DC voltage	V	1400	100 - 1500	LVDC voltage level
DC config	-	bipolar	unipolar bipolar	DC system configuration
Load scaling factor	-	1.3	0 – 5	Model heat pumps or additional customers
Load eff. gain	%	10	0 – 30	Household load efficiency gain if connected to LVDC
PV	%	30	0 – 100	PV penetration (Fn. of nr. of loads)
PV eff. gain	%	1	0 – 30	PV efficiency gain if connected to LVDC
EV	%	80	0 – 100	EV penetration (Fn. of nr. of households)
EV eff. gain	%	1	0 – 30	EV efficiency gain if connected to LVDC
AC topology	-	radial	radial meshed	Topology for AC LV grid
DC scenario	-	2	1a / 1b / 2	ACDC hybrid scenario
VSC1 eff.	-	0.98	0.8 – 1	VSC 1 efficiency
VSC2 eff.	-	-	0.8 – 1	VSC 2 efficiency (only applies to scenario 1)
VSC rated power ratio	-	0.9	0.7 – 1	VSC rated power (max. feeder / max. household load for VSC2)

peaks of short duration, the voltage profile depicted in Figure 8 reveals recurrent violations of the prescribed minimum voltage threshold of 0.9 per unit, as stipulated by EN 50160, occurring throughout the day. This persistent issue with voltage regulation can be effectively resolved through the conversion of the feeder to a 1400 V_{DC} system.

Likewise, the voltage profile for feeder LV rural 1 on June 23th (as depicted in Figure 9) demonstrates the inability to maintain compliance with the specified voltage tolerance band when utilizing a 400 V_{AC} system within the provided scenario.

Despite the fact that converting most LV feeders to a DC configuration does not result in an overall reduction of losses within the provided scenario, primarily due to the elevated no-load losses associated with VSC and the predominantly low-load operational conditions of LV feeders, Figure 10 demonstrates that the efficiency enhancements associated with the integration of EV and PV into the DC network yield a significant reduction in the maximum apparent power

Figure 6: Maximum Loading of LV feeder yearly simulation

Figure 7: LV urban 3 daily max. loading profile, Sept 16

input to the feeder, denoted as S_{in_max} .

Figure 8: LV urban 3 daily min/max voltage, Sept 16.

Figure 9: LV rural 1 daily min/max voltage profile, Jun 23.

Figure 10: Maximum LV feeder input apparent power

3 Simulation Model

To perform system simulations of a hybrid ACDC microgrid connected to the public distribution grid, the Terni pilot installation (WP8) was chosen to be used. Furthermore, the availability of grid data at the pilot site allows a high-quality remodeling of the system. The Terni pilot site was modeled in Power Factory because the simulation tool lacks the capability to simulate the ACDC microgrid with two connection points via transformers. Hence, the simulation results will be of further use within the HYPERRIDE project.

In this section, it is explained how the simulation model, its components and power flow profiles were derived.

3.1 AC Grid Model

The AC grid, comprising both MV and LV components, encompasses a span of 2200 meters of MV lines. These MV lines are interlinked with the LVDG through five MV-LV transformers. The grid data for the AC feeder, where the ACDC microgrid will be connected, was provided by ASM and then remodeled in Power Factory. Figure 11 shows the Power Factory model of the AC grid. A comprehensive and detailed description of both the AC grid and the ACDC microgrid can be accessed within the contents of the HYPERRIDE deliverable D8.2.

The ACDC microgrid will be connected through two Active Front End (AFE) at nodes 8 and 12.

3.2 ACDC Microgrid Model

The ACDC microgrid incorporates a PV system with a peak power of 10 kW, alongside a battery unit capable of delivering 40 kW of active power and storing 21 kWh of energy. Additionally, the microgrid encompasses an EV charger, possessing a maximum power output of 40 kW. Within the microgrid, a vital component is the critical AC load, characterized by a peak power consumption of 1.5 kW. Figure 12 shows a conceptual representation of the ACDC microgrid configuration.

3.3 Power Flow Profiles

To perform QDS using power factory, all components of the grid have to be fed with a load flow profile for active and reactive load. The yearly load profiles for the AC grid, aggregated at each LV substation, were provided in ten minutes resolution characteristics by ASM. Therefore, the profiles for the ACDC microgrid components have to be provided in the same resolution to perform full year load flow simulations.

3.3.1 AC Critical Loads

The load profiles for active and reactive power of the AC critical load was provided by Terni and represents a realistic estimation of how the load curve of the connected loads will look like. The peak load is 1.5 kW. Figure 13 shows the yearly load profile of the critical AC load in MW.

Figure 11: Terni MV Feeder Power Factory Model.

3.3.2 PV and Battery Profile

The profiles of the PV and BESS were generated using the Component Sizing Tool presented in the HYPERRIDE deliverable D3.4. The operational strategy of the BESS within the Component Sizing Tool is oriented towards optimizing self-consumption. This implies that the energy produced onsite is primarily intended for immediate onsite utilization. Any surplus energy generated beyond the immediate on-site consumption is directed towards storage in the BESS. Export to the grid is only contemplated when the BESS is fully charged. In instances where on-site generation falls short of concurrent consumption, the BESS will discharge until the Depth of Discharge (DoD) is reached. Grid usage is only initiated as a backup when the BESS is fully discharged and on-site consumption persists.

Input data for the Component Sizing Tool involves the critical AC loads and EV load, offering flexibility in selecting the dimensions of the PV system and BESS. In this scenario, components on the pilot site in Terni were remodeled to match the setup. A PV with 10 kW peak power and a 40 kW power output battery with a 21 kWh capacity were selected. In accordance with the previously described operational strategy, the tool generates the PV profile and delineates the charge and discharge profiles of the BESS.

In Figure 14, the active power profiles of the elements within the ACDC microgrid are de-

Figure 12: Terni Pilot ACDC microgrid concept.

Figure 13: Terni Pilot AC critical loads profile (in MW) connected to hybrid ACDC microgrid.

picted for February 24th. The visual representation showcases the distinctive charge and discharge dynamics of the BESS, effectively enhancing self-consumption through optimization strategies.

3.3.3 EV Charging Profile

The EV charging profiles were generated using an Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT) internal EV charging profile generator. Further information can be found in (Stahleder, Übermasser, Reih, Ledinger, & Lehfuss, 2021) and (Stahleder et al., 2018). As input for the EV charging profile generator the following parameters were chosen:

- 40 kW peak power
- 1 vehicle

Figure 14: Total Active Power of the components in the ACDC microgrid.

- office building

The Figure 15 shows the loading profile for a single day, with January 31st being shown here.

Figure 15: Terni Pilot EV load profile (in MW) connected to hybrid ACDC microgrid.

3.4 Complete Simulation Model

In finalizing the simulation model, integration of the ACDC microgrid occurs via two AFEs situated at nodes 8 and 12. Figure 16 illustrates the comprehensive Power Factory model depicting the interconnection of the AC grid with the ACDC microgrid.

Figure 16: Power Factory model of AC grid with ACDC microgrid connected.

3.5 Scenarios

In the first scenario, the investigation consists of two aspects. First, the assessment of the AC grid in isolation and then, its connection with the ACDC microgrid is conducted. In this scenario, the AFEs are configured to exclusively deliver active power, similar to the setup at the Terni demo site. This assessment primarily centers on the analysis of terminal voltages and the loading conditions experienced by the MV-LV transformer.

In the second scenario, the setup of the AFEs undergoes a modification. On one hand, they are now capable of supplying reactive power, and on the other, their power rating is doubled. This adjustment enables the analysis of terminal voltages and loading conditions, allowing for a comparison with the outcomes of the initial scenario.

The third and final scenario involves an extensive investigation aimed at determining the optimal configuration for the ACDC microgrid. This investigation includes the systematic variation of all components within the ACDC microgrid. The desired optimization concerns the maximization of self-consumption, which is represented by the parameters PV self-consumption and the energy self-sufficiency of the local grid. The process includes individual adjustments to each component, followed by a joint optimization step to determine the most efficient overall configuration.

3.6 Results

In the subsequent sections, the simulation outcomes involving the grid model and the scenarios described earlier are elucidated. In the initial scenario, our attention is directed towards monitoring the voltage levels at both the LV and MV terminals within the AC grid throughout the span of a year. Illustrated in Figure 17, the voltage measurements at these terminals are presented in per unit (p.u.). Notably, it becomes apparent that the prescribed minimum threshold of 0.9 p.u., as dictated by the EN 50160 standard, is violated multiple times under the annual duration, even if these violations could be compensated by varying the ratio of the MV/LV transformers.

Figure 17: Voltage levels of the LV and MV terminals over a year.

To illustrate the utilization of components in the AC grid, we examine the MV-LV transformer 5. Figure 18 shows the loading of the MV-LV transformer 5 over the course of a year, expressed in percentage. It is noteworthy that there are occasional spikes that lead to utilization rates of over 100%. Subsequently, we proceed to examine these identical plots with the ACDC microgrid integrated into the AC grid. Initially, we compare with the configuration mirroring the Terni demonstration site. In this configuration, the AFEs exclusively deliver active power. Figure 19 showcases the voltage profiles of both LV and MV terminals, now in conjunction with the ACDC microgrid. Unfortunately, the voltage violations remain unchanged, indicating that the ACDC microgrid, in its initial configuration, is incapable of supporting the AC grid. Figure 20 shows the loading of the MV-LV transformer 5 with the connected ACDC microgrid. Once again, we observe a consistent pattern where the utilization of the MV-LV transformer 5 remains unchanged, just as it did when the system was solely connected to the AC grid.

In the second scenario, the AFEs have been adapted to provide reactive power support. We can now contrast this modified scenario with the initial one. In Figure 21a, voltage levels at both the LV and MV terminals are displayed. In Figure 21b, we examine the same parameters, but this time, we have doubled the rated power of the AFEs. It is evident that the provision

Figure 18: Loading of the MV-LV transformer 5 over a year.

Figure 19: Voltage levels of the LV and MV terminals over a year with ACDC microgrid connected.

of reactive power through the AFEs contributes to the stabilization of the AC grid, resulting in reduced voltage drops. Doubling the rated power of the converters leads to a reduction in voltage violations, with the limit of 0.9 p.u. being undercut less frequently, with the exception of

Figure 20: Loading of the MV-LV transformer 5 over a year with ACDC microgrid connected.

(a) Voltage levels of the LV and MV terminals over a year with ACDC microgrid connected with PQ support of the AFEs. (b) Voltage levels of the LV and MV terminals over a year with ACDC microgrid connected with PQ support and rated power twofold of the AFEs.

Figure 21: Comparison of the LV and MV terminals with different configuration of the AFEs.

LV terminal 3. Figure 22a illustrates the loading of the MV-LV transformer 5 with converters that have been adjusted to supply reactive power. In Figure 22b, the rated power of the AFEs has been doubled. In both Figures, it is evident that the loading has decreased in comparison to the initial scenario, and the utilization remains below 100 percent. In a direct comparison over a 24-hour period on January 28th, Figure 23 illustrates that the loading of the MV-LV transformer 5 for those four setups is consistently lower on average, not only during peak times when the AFEs support the AC grid with reactive power. The two setups, "only AC grid" in red and "with ACDC microgrid only P," result in the same utilization of the MV-LV transformer. It is also evident that the difference between the single and double power rating of the converters is almost negligible

(a) Loading of the MV-LV transformer 5 over a year with ACDC microgrid connected with PQ support of the AFEs. (b) Loading of the MV-LV transformer 5 over a year with ACDC microgrid connected with PQ support and rated power twofold of the AFEs.

Figure 22: Comparison of the MV-LV transformer 5 loading with different configuration of the AFEs.

for the utilization of the MV-LV transformer 5.

Figure 23: Direct comparison of the loading of the MV-LV transformer 5 over a day.

In the third and final scenario, an in-depth investigation was conducted to identify the optimal configuration for the ACDC microgrid. The goal of this investigation was to enhance self-consumption, which was assessed using two key parameters: PV self-consumption and energy self-sufficiency. The findings are expressed as percentages. The investigation consisted of systematically varying all components within the ACDC microgrid. Each component underwent individual adjustments to assess its impact on overall performance. Following individual component adjustments, a joint optimization process was executed. This step aimed to deter-

mine the most efficient overall configuration by considering the interplay of all components. The goal was to achieve the highest possible self-consumption while minimizing reliance on the AC grid.

Figure 24a shows that the sum of PV self-consumption and energy self-sufficiency reveals a maximum at 10 kW AC loads. After this analysis, the variable of EV load was subjected to investigation. In Figure 24b, a discernible pattern emerges: at an EV load of 40 kW, the self-consumption of PV-generated energy does not increase significantly anymore. However, as EV load surpasses this threshold, the self-sufficiency experiences a noticeable decline. This relationship indicates that an optimal balance exists between the energy demand of EVs and PV self-consumption, with exceeding EV loads correlating with diminished energy self-sufficiency, as depicted in the data presented in Figure 24b.

Next the PV generation was adjusted. The data depicted in Figure 24c indicates that greater PV generation leads to a decrease in PV self-consumption, while concurrently causing an increase in energy self-sufficiency of the local grid.

Final component analysis in the ACDC microgrid focuses on the BESS, with a specific examination of battery power and capacity. Figure 24d illustrates the effects of varying battery power, revealing that at 30 kW, the combination of PV self-consumption and self-sufficiency reveals a maximum. Subsequently, Figure 24e portrays the impact of varying battery capacity. Notably, a larger battery capacity corresponds to increased PV self-consumption and energy self-sufficiency of the local grid. From a strictly technical standpoint, identifying an outright optimum configuration proves challenging. However, it is observable that the incremental benefits begin to diminish beyond 21 kWh. Especially when examining PV self-consumption and comparing the increase from 10 kWh to 21 kWh and then from 21 kWh to 30 kWh, we observe that the gain in PV self-consumption has halved.

What is the form of the common optimum emerging from the interplay of these components within the ACDC microgrid? Based on the preceding outcomes derived from the individual component variations within the ACDC microgrid, the resulting configuration is as follows: allocating 10 kW for AC loads, 40 kW for EV loads, and configuring the battery with a power output of 30 kW and a capacity of 21 kWh. For the sizing of the PV, a renewed investigation into the PV component is being conducted. In the context of the newly introduced scenario depicted in Figure 24f, a recognisable trend emerges with regards to the variation in PV generation. It becomes apparent that an increase in PV generation is inversely correlated with PV self-consumption, leading to an enhancement in the self-sufficiency of the local grid. This aligns with the observations analyzed in Figure 24c. The combination of PV self-consumption and self-sufficiency reaches a peak at 10 kW. Therefore the currently installed PV power of 10 kW seems to be a promising parameter.

(a) Variation AC loads

(b) Variation EV load

(c) Variation PV generation

(d) Variation battery power

(e) Variation battery capacity

(f) Variation PV generation in combined scenario

Figure 24: Variation of all components within the ACDC microgrid.

4 Conclusions

In this section, we aim to consolidate the outcomes derived from both the simulation model and simulation tool, while also examining their correlation. We start with the outcomes derived from the simulation tool. The provided simulation tool offers the advantage of flexible and rapid hybridization of intricate grid models within Power Factory. The chosen simulation results have emphasized the potential advantages of employing DC technology within the LV grid. In instances where the capacity limits of an LVAC system are approached, the study has demonstrated that converting the LV feeder to DC, as opposed to reinforcing the existing lines, can yield benefits. This holds true for both rural and urban LV feeders, particularly when considering the anticipated advancements in DC equipment. Future research endeavors are planned to explore the flexibility of the tool towards scalability and replicability. These investigations will facilitate an examination of potential impacts on the overarching AC grid resulting from hybridization and the identification of synergies to address forthcoming challenges, such as low inertia grids or the management of decentralized energy communities.

Moving on to the outcomes obtained from the Terni simulation model, we have described three distinct scenarios for our investigation. We conducted an extensive analysis of terminal voltages and the loading conditions experienced by the MV-LV transformer. In this analysis, we examined four distinct setups:

1. The AC Grid alone;
2. The AC Grid with the ACDC microgrid connected, where the AFEs supply active power;
3. The AC Grid with the ACDC microgrid connected, where the AFEs supply both active and reactive power;
4. The AC Grid with the ACDC microgrid connected, where the AFEs supply both active and reactive power, with a doubled rated power.

The analysis revealed that, the AFE plays a decisive role in AC grid support by the DC grid, as shown by the current AC grid and the proposed DC configuration. For this demo site, it is imperative that the converters possess the capability to provide reactive power to support the AC grid effectively. This solution is instrumental in mitigating voltage violations and lowering the utilization rates experienced by the MV-LV transformers. The integration of peak shaving in the BESS within the ACDC microgrid could allow for the inclusion of larger PV systems without overloading the AC grid. We also made extensive investigations with the primary objective of identifying the optimal configuration for the ACDC microgrid. Our goal was to achieve the highest level of self-consumption while minimizing reliance on the AC grid. The resulting optimal configuration allowed for the integration of more AC loads and a reduction in the required battery power output.

In our upcoming investigations, we plan to incorporate the insights gained from the results of the simulation model. As the next step, we intend to raise the voltage level of the DC system to 1400 V_{DC} bipolar configuration. A $\pm 700 V_{DC}$ system significantly enhances the hosting capacity of the network compared to the standard 3-phase 400 V_{AC} setup. However, there are currently no commercially available components for 1500 V_{DC} . Further investigation is also required to examine the converter control system's ability to provide DC stabilization and AC support. It also needs to be assessed for more dynamic control behavior.

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